

EFFECT OF INTERNATIONAL PUBLIC SECTOR ACCOUNTING STANDARD (IPSAS) IN PUBLIC SECTOR IN ANAMBRA STATE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14245673>

Abstract: *The study determined the effect of international public sector accounting standard (IPSAS) in public sector in Anambra state. Descriptive cross-sectional survey research design was utilized in the study. The population of the study was made up of 244 full-time staff of selected public organisations in Awka Metropolis from which a sample size of 152 respondents were chosen. In this study, primary data were collected using self-administered questionnaires. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman Ranked Order Correlation Coefficient, which was calculated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25. The study revealed that the adoption of IPSAS significantly enhances the comparability of financial statements among public sector entities in Anambra State. The study also found that the adoption of IPSAS significantly facilitates better decision-making processes among public sector entities in Anambra State. The study recommends among others that the State Accountant General's Office should establish a centralized framework for monitoring and evaluating the compliance of public sector entities with IPSAS.*

Keywords: *IPSAS, Comparability, Decision-Making, Public Sector*

Introduction

The implementation of robust accounting standards is crucial for enhancing those aspects, and the adoption of international Public area Accounting requirements (IPSAS) represents a important step toward reaching this goal (Ezejiofor, Okolocha & Ofurum, 2020). IPSAS are designed to enhance the first-rate of general-reason economic reporting through public region entities, thereby increasing transparency and duty (Zibaghafa & Okpolosa, 2024). The standards are issued by way of the worldwide Public Sector Accounting Standards Board (IPSASB) and are meant to be applied through entities that prepare economic statements in accordance with accrual-primarily based accounting. The adoption of IPSAS is predicted to lead to higher monetary control practices, decorate the comparability of financial statements, and facilitate better choice-making procedures (Abatcha, 2024). In Nigeria, mainly in Anambra state, the adoption of IPSAS is seen as a tremendous flow toward improving public zone monetary management and aligning with global exceptional practices.

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 12 Issue 4, October-December 2024

ISSN: 2837-1070

Impact Factor: 6.65

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Compliance with IPSAS is applicable for several reasons since it complements the great of monetary reporting via ensuring that economic statements are prepared on a regular and comparable foundation (Hussaini, 2024). This uniformity is crucial for stakeholders, which includes government officials, investors, creditors, and the general public, who depend on those economic statements to make knowledgeable selections. Secondly, IPSAS compliance promotes more accountability and transparency inside the control of public sources (Ezejiofor, Okolocha & Ofurum, 2020). via adhering to those requirements, public area entities are required to offer complete and accurate information approximately their monetary function and overall performance, which enables to build trust and credibility.

Furthermore, adherence to IPSAS is also seen as a way to attract foreign investment and aid, as it signals a commitment to international standards of financial management and governance. IPSAS were developed by the International Public Sector Accounting Standards Board (IPSASB) to address the unique financial reporting needs of public sector entities (Abatcha, 2024). These standards are based on the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) issued by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), but are tailored to the public sector context. IPSAS cover various aspects of financial reporting, including the recognition, measurement, presentation, and disclosure of financial information (Zibaghafa & Okpolosa, 2024). The main concepts of IPSAS revolve around the principles of accrual accounting, which requires entities to recognize transactions and events when they occur, rather than when cash or its equivalent is received or paid. This approach provides a more accurate picture of an entity's financial position and performance, as it includes information about assets, liabilities, revenues, and expenses that are not captured under cash-based accounting. Additionally, IPSAS emphasize the importance of transparency and accountability in financial reporting, encouraging public sector entities to provide clear and comprehensive information about their financial activities (Adedeji, 2024).

Another significant impact of IPSAS adoption is the improvement of financial management practices. The standards provide a framework for the systematic recording and reporting of financial transactions, which helps to ensure that public resources are managed efficiently and effectively. This improved financial management can lead to better allocation of resources, reduced waste and corruption, and enhanced public service delivery (Alessa, 2024). IPSAS also facilitates better comparability of financial information across different entities and jurisdictions. This comparability is important for benchmarking and performance evaluation, as it allows stakeholders to assess the financial health and performance of different public sector entities on a consistent basis (Alkhabbaz & Suresh, 2023). In Nigeria, this has implications for intergovernmental fiscal relations, as it enables the federal and state governments to monitor and evaluate the financial performance of various entities more effectively. Thus, the adoption of International Public Sector Accounting Standards in Nigeria, particularly in Anambra State, represents a significant step towards improving public sector financial management.

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The relevance of IPSAS compliance lies in its ability to enhance financial transparency, accountability, and comparability, which are essential for building trust and credibility (Alkhabbaz & Suresh, 2023).

The failure to fully implement IPSAS in the Nigerian public sector has several negative consequences. Firstly, the lack of transparency and accountability in financial reporting undermines public trust in government institutions. Stakeholders, including citizens and international partners, may perceive the public sector as being prone to corruption and mismanagement, which can erode confidence and support. Secondly, the inefficiencies in financial management due to non-compliance with IPSAS can lead to poor resource allocation, wastage, and reduced effectiveness of public service delivery (Alessa, 2024). This situation hampers the socio-economic development of the state and the country at large. Lastly, the inability to produce reliable and comparable financial information can limit Nigeria's ability to attract foreign investment and aid, as international donors and financial institutions often require adherence to international accounting standards. This could further constrain the financial resources available for critical development projects and initiatives in Anambra State and across Nigeria.

The main objective of the study is to examine the influence of international public sector accounting standard in public sector in Anambra state. The specific objectives are:

- i. To ascertain the extent to which the adoption of IPSAS enhances the comparability of financial statements among public sector entities in Anambra state.
- ii. To examine the degree to which the adoption of IPSAS facilitates better decision-making processes among public sector entities in Anambra state.

Conceptual Review

International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS)

The importance of IPSAS lies in its ability to enhance governance and responsibility in the public quarter (Okpara, Eke & Ajobor, 2023). In many nations, public quarter monetary control has traditionally been plagued by way of inconsistencies, lack of transparency, and terrible financial reporting practices. IPSAS provides a standardized method to financial reporting that helps to rectify those troubles by way of requiring entities to stick to principles that sell accuracy, reliability, and relevance in their economic statements. This standardization is specifically important for nations looking for to improve their monetary control practices, appeal to investment, and benefit the self-assurance of global donors and economic establishments. Through adopting IPSAS, governments can exhibit their commitment to sound monetary governance and enhance the trust of residents and different stakeholders in public monetary management (Okpara, Eke & Ajobor, 2023).

Furthermore, IPSAS performs a critical role in permitting higher decision-making in the public quarter. Correct and obvious financial information is essential for making knowledgeable coverage decisions, allocating resources effectively, and assessing the financial sustainability of presidency applications (Oluwayemisi, Alade, Awe & Akinyosoye, 2024). IPSAS allows making certain that the monetary statements of public quarter entities offer a true and honest view of their economic position and overall performance, which, in flip, helps sound selection-making approaches (Zibaghafa & Okpolosa, 2024). Additionally, IPSAS helps the comparison of financial statistics across one of kind jurisdictions and over time, permitting governments and global agencies to evaluate and compare the financial health and performance of public area entities globally.

Comparability of Financial Statements

Comparability of financial statements refers to the capacity to reliably assess and contrast financial information across different organizations or time periods due to the application of standardized accounting principles and practices (Okpara, Eke & Ajobor, 2023). This comparability is a fundamental qualitative characteristic of financial reporting that enhances the utility of financial statements for users, such as investors, regulators, and other stakeholders (Abata, 2022). When financial statements are comparable, users can evaluate the financial performance and position of different entities, assess trends over time, and make informed economic decisions based on consistent and comparable data (Alkhabbaz & Suresh, 2023).

The concept of comparability is closely tied to the adoption and implementation of standardized accounting frameworks. These frameworks provide a common set of rules and guidelines that organizations must follow when preparing their financial statements. By adhering to these standards, organizations ensure that their financial statements are prepared on a consistent basis, which facilitates comparability across different entities and jurisdictions. Without standardized accounting practices, financial statements could be prepared using different methodologies, making it difficult or impossible for users to compare financial data accurately.

Comparability also extends to the consistency of financial reporting within an organization over time (Zibaghafa & Chukwu, 2024). This means that an organization should apply the same accounting policies and procedures from one period to the next unless there is a valid reason to change them, such as a change in accounting standards or the need to reflect a more accurate financial picture. Consistency in accounting practices ensures that users can track an organization's financial performance and position over time, identify trends, and assess the impact of management decisions on financial outcomes. If an organization frequently changes its accounting policies, it can undermine the comparability of its financial statements and reduce the confidence of users in the reliability of the financial information provided.

Decision-Making Processes

Decision-making processes are the structured activities and procedures through which individuals or organizations evaluate options and make choices to achieve specific objectives (Rijal, 2023). These processes are fundamental to all aspects of human life and organizational functioning, as decisions shape the actions that lead to desired outcomes. In the context of organizations, decision-making processes are critical for strategic planning, resource allocation, problem-solving, and the overall management of operations. Effective decision-making processes involve the identification of goals, the collection and analysis of relevant information, the consideration of alternative courses of action, and the selection of the best option based on a rational evaluation of the potential outcomes (Sari, 2023).

The decision-making process typically begins with the recognition of a need or a problem that requires a decision (Rijal, 2023). This stage involves identifying the objectives that the decision aims to achieve and the constraints or limitations that must be considered. For example, in a business setting, the need to increase market share might prompt a decision-making process aimed at selecting the best marketing strategy. The clarity of objectives at this stage is crucial, as it guides the subsequent steps in the decision-making process.

Once the objectives are defined, the next step involves gathering and analyzing relevant information. This information can come from various sources, including internal data, market research, expert opinions, and historical records. The quality and completeness of the information collected play a significant role in the effectiveness of the decision-making process (Sari, 2023). Incomplete or inaccurate information can lead to poor decisions, while comprehensive and accurate data provide a solid foundation for evaluating the available options. After gathering the necessary information, the decision-making process moves to the evaluation of alternative courses of action. This stage involves considering the potential outcomes of each option, weighing the pros and cons, and assessing the risks and benefits associated with each alternative. Decision-makers may use various analytical tools and techniques, such as cost-benefit analysis, scenario planning, or decision trees, to systematically evaluate the options (Rijal, 2023). The goal is to identify the option that best aligns with the objectives and constraints identified earlier in the process.

Empirical Review

Adedeji (2024) examined the factors affecting the adoption of IPSAS in the South Western States of Nigeria. A well-structured questionnaire was used to gather information from prospective respondents who are accounting officers in the public service of the states in the geopolitical zone. The data were analyzed using both descriptive statistics and Structural Equation Modelling. The results indicate that normative (interest group political power, resources, and capacity) and coercive (from federal government, international institutions, and the state fiscal imbalance) factors influenced the adoption of IPSAS in the sample states.

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 12 Issue 4, October-December 2024

ISSN: 2837-1070

Impact Factor: 6.65

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Zibaghafa and Chukwu (2024) ascertained public sector accounting standards adoption and the quality of financial reporting in higher institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States, Nigeria.. Primary and secondary sources of data were employed, while univariate and multivariate analyses were used for data analysis. The multivariate analysis revealed that Pre- and Post-IPSAS adoption has no significant difference in the financial reporting of relevance, while faithful representation, understandability, timeliness, verifiability, and comparability showed significant differences in the Pre- and Post-IPSAS adoption periods in the higher institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa State. The study concluded that the Pre- and Post-IPSAS periods have no significant influence on the relevance of higher institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States. Both Pre- and Post-IPSAS adoption periods have a significant difference in influencing faithful representation, understandability, timeliness, and verifiability of higher institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Alessa (2024) tested the effect of adopting international Public sector accounting standards (IPSAS) on the aid allocation performance of growing countries. A strong econometric modeling, inclusive of fixed effect and two-Step generalized technique of Moments, is hired on a pattern of sixty four growing nations between 2005 and 2021. The findings suggest that the IPSAS coefficient is substantially and positively correlated at a 5% degree or higher. This shows a strong and tremendous courting among IPSAS adoption and useful resource allocation, indicating that the use of IPSAS improves green aid allocation. moreover, the resource allocation coefficient is advantageous and surprisingly giant at a five% degree or better.

Onodi and Utuk (2023) assessed the quantity to which IPSAS engenders monetary reporting excellent in Nigeria. The study's populace consisted of 426 employees of Federal government corporations in FCT, Abuja, with a pattern length of 206 personnel. a complete of 206 questionnaires had been dispensed, and 200 validly back copies had been used for the analysis. The facts were analyzed the use of a regression version. The end result shows that IPSAS has a sizeable positive impact on the transparency of the Nigerian public region's financial reports. Furthermore, the adoption of IPSAS has a minor terrible have an effect on on the reliability of economic reports inside the Nigerian public sector. in the end, it's miles found that IPSAS implementation has a sizeable useful affect at the fee relevance of economic reports.

Alkhabbaz and Suresh (2023) determined the effect of adopting international Public region Accounting standards (IPSAS) at the comparability of financial reviews within the public region of India. To reap this, each number one and secondary assets of information have been used. A nicely-designed questionnaire based totally on a 5-point Likert scale turned into employed to acquire primary data from bills branch employees of Public quarter companies (PSEs) in India. One hundred questionnaires had been distributed, and seventy five have been lower back, which shaped the sample size at a 5% level of significance. SPSS software become employed to investigate the amassed facts, and Spearman's correlation take a look at became used for checking out the speculation. The look at found that the

adoption of IPSAS has a substantially positive effect on the comparability of financial reports inside the public zone of India, as it increases this level.

Olaru (2023) ascertained the practical improvement in the quality of financial reporting in Romanian public institutions after implementing IPSAS. A questionnaire addressed to accounting professionals in the local public administration was used, with 164 respondents participating. A linear regression analysis method was employed to examine the relationship between the implementation of IPSAS and the quality of financial reporting in Romanian public institutions. The introduction of IPSAS was found to be significantly positively related to the quality of financial reporting in Romanian public institutions. Balogun and Fatogun (2022) examined the impact of IPSAS adoption on financial accountability, transparency, and credibility of financial management at the local government level in Ogun State. Primary data was collected from three local governments, with thirty questionnaires administered to conveniently selected members of the Accounting, Internal Audit, and Finance departments across the selected local governments. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses on the impact of IPSAS adoption on financial accountability and transparency in local government in Nigeria. The results show that IPSAS adoption has a significantly positive impact on financial accountability ($t=8.117$; $p=.006$) and the credibility of financial management at the local government level ($t=1.221$; $p=.002$). However, IPSAS has no significant impact on transparency ($t=2.932$; $p=.091$).

Al-Kharabsheh (2021) examined the effect of adopting International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) on financial performance in the Jordanian public sector, aiming to reform its accounting system to control public money. The study is significant due to its timing during Jordan's difficult economic and financial conditions and the government's consideration of IPSAS adoption as an entrepreneurial move. Descriptive and inferential approaches were applied for data analysis. A questionnaire was designed to collect data from accountants in the Ministry of Finance and analyzed using SPSS. One key result is that adopting IPSAS on an accrual basis enhances transparency, credibility, reliability, and full disclosure of financial statements.

Beredugo (2021) diagnosed the demanding situations of IPSAS implementation inside the Nigerian public zone. A based questionnaire turned into used to accumulate information from accountants, auditors, and coins officers in authorities ministries, departments, and groups throughout 5 states: Abia, Anambra, Enugu, Ebonyi, and Imo. The populace changed into envisioned at 8,901, with a sample length of 387 drawn the use of the stratified sampling method. Evaluation of Variance (ANOVA) was used for hypothesis testing. Consequences indicated that demanding situations to complete IPSAS implementation encompass a lack of political will, statutory adjustments, insufficient investment, and insufficient institutional commitment.

Ezejiofor, Okolocha, and Ofurum (2020) examined the extent to which adopting IPSAS helps curb corrupt practices among public officers in Enugu State. A survey research design was adopted, involving

a sample from a population of 127 staff members in the Enugu State Ministry of Finance. Using Taro Yamane's formula, a sample size of 96 was determined. Data were analyzed using frequency counts and mean scores, and hypotheses were tested using the t-test statistical tool with SPSS version 20.0 at a 5% significance level. The study revealed that adopting IPSAS reduces corruption among public officers.

Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional survey research design was utilized. By adopting this design, the study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the subjects under investigation, allowing for an in-depth exploration of their characteristics and behaviors at a single point in time.

The population of the study comprised all the full-time staff of the three selected public organisations in Awka Metropolis. The three purposively selected public organisations are Anambra Broadcasting Service (ABS), Anambra State Housing Development Corporation, and Anambra State Water Corporation, all in Awka. The population target of the study is given below in 244.

The sampling technique employed to select the participants was purposive sampling. This method was chosen to focus on public organizations that were geographically close to the researcher, facilitating easier data collection. The three public organizations were specifically selected due to the ease of accessing data from them. From a total population of 244, the sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's (1964) formula for sample size determination in finite populations. According to Yamane (1964), the sample size for a finite population is calculated using the following formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n - Sample size

N - Population size

e - The level of precision, sometimes called sampling error, is the range in which the true value of the population is estimated to be.

1 - Constant

Therefore;

Substituting the values in the formula where e = 5% we have:

$$N = 244$$

$$e = 0.05$$

$$n = ?$$

$$n = \frac{244}{1+244(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{244}{1+244(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{244}{1+0.61}$$

$$n = \frac{244}{1.61}$$

$$n = 151.55$$

Approximately, $n = 152$

Method of Data Collection

Instrument for Data Collection

In this study, primary data were collected using self-administered questionnaires composed of closed-ended questions. The questionnaire was carefully designed with a 5-point Likert scale to assess various constructs. This format provided respondents with the convenience to complete the survey at their own pace, thereby improving the accuracy and reliability of their answers. The choice to use a questionnaire was based on its ability to standardize data.

Method of Data Analysis

The study's descriptive statistical analysis utilized measures such as mean, frequency counts, and percentages. These statistical methods were chosen for their simplicity and ease of interpretation. In contrast, the inferential statistical analysis aimed to assess the study's null hypotheses. To achieve this, the researcher employed the Spearman Ranked Order Correlation Coefficient, which was calculated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25.

Decision Rule

The hypotheses testing were carried out with a significance level of 5%. If the p-value of the test is higher than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, if the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, the alternative hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Analysis of Mean Scores for the Variables

Table 1: Presentation of Mean Scores for the Variable: Comparability of Financial Statements

S/N	Statements About the Research Variable	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean
1	IPSAS adoption improves the comparison of our financial statements with the ones of different public region entities.	34	32	0	71	0	3.21
2	The adoption of IPSAS permits for more consistent financial reporting throughout exclusive departments.	113	21	0	3	0	4.78
3	The adoption of IPSAS has facilitated better contrast of monetary performance throughout fiscal years.	29	89	0	19	0	3.93
4	IPSAS has advanced the capacity to examine monetary statistics between various public quarter organizations.	23	68	0	46	0	3.5

Source: Survey Findings, 2024

Table 1 presents the mean scores for various statements related to the comparability of financial statements following the adoption of the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS). Each statement reflects different aspects of how IPSAS influences the ability of organizations to compare their financial reporting.

The first statement suggests that IPSAS adoption improves the comparability of financial statements with those of other public sector entities. It received a mean score of 3.21, indicating a generally neutral to positive response. While 34 respondents strongly agreed and 32 agreed, the significant number of 71 individuals who disagreed suggests that there are notable concerns regarding how well IPSAS facilitates comparability. This mixed feedback indicates that while some see benefits, many remain skeptical.

In contrast, the second statement asserts that the adoption of IPSAS allows for more consistent financial reporting across different departments, achieving an impressive mean score of 4.78. The overwhelming support is evidenced by 113 respondents who strongly agreed, with only 3 disagreeing. This strong consensus indicates a widespread belief that IPSAS significantly enhances consistency in financial reporting, which is crucial for effective organizational performance.

The third statement examines whether IPSAS has facilitated better comparison of financial performance across fiscal years, yielding a mean score of 3.93. This score reflects a favorable view, with 29 respondents strongly agreeing and 89 agreeing. The relatively small number of disagreements (19) suggests that there is a strong perception that IPSAS enhances the ability to compare financial results over time, contributing positively to financial analysis and decision-making.

The final statement focuses on whether IPSAS has improved the ability to compare financial data between various public sector organizations, which received a mean score of 3.5. This score indicates a moderate level of agreement, with 23 strong agreements and 68 general agreements, yet also accompanied by 46 disagreements. This suggests that while many recognize improvements in comparability across organizations, there remains a considerable portion of respondents who question the effectiveness of IPSAS in this regard.

Table 2: Presentation of Mean Scores for the Variable: Decision-Making Processes

S/N	Statements About the Research Variable	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean
5	The adoption of IPSAS has provided greater dependable economic statistics for decision-making.	33	52	2	50	0	3.50
6	IPSAS implementation has more desirable the high-quality of economic facts to be had for strategic selections.	95	0	0	42	0	4.08
7	IPSAS has facilitated quicker and greater accurate economic selections in our public zone entity.	1	136	0	0	0	4.01
8	The adoption of IPSAS has advanced the alignment of economic selections with organizational dreams.	18	45	0	73	1	3.04

Source: Survey Findings, 2024

Table 2 presents the mean scores for various statements regarding the impact of the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) on decision-making processes within organizations. Each

statement sheds light on how IPSAS influences the reliability and quality of financial data used in making strategic decisions.

The first statement suggests that IPSAS adoption has provided more reliable financial data for decision-making, achieving a mean score of 3.50. This score indicates a generally positive perception, with 33 respondents strongly agreeing and 52 agreeing. However, the presence of 50 individuals who disagreed points to some skepticism about the reliability of the financial data being provided, highlighting a divide in experiences regarding IPSAS's impact on decision-making.

The second statement claims that IPSAS implementation has enhanced the quality of financial information available for strategic decisions, which garnered a mean score of 4.08. This high score is supported by a significant number of respondents (95) who strongly agreed, reflecting a strong consensus that IPSAS improves the quality of information necessary for strategic planning. The absence of neutral or disagreeing responses further emphasizes the perceived effectiveness of IPSAS in enhancing financial information quality.

The third statement assesses whether IPSAS has facilitated quicker and more accurate financial decisions within the organization. With a mean score of 4.01, this statement received overwhelming support, as indicated by 136 respondents who agreed. The absence of disagreement suggests a strong belief among participants that IPSAS contributes positively to the speed and accuracy of financial decision-making processes.

The final statement examines whether the adoption of IPSAS has improved the alignment of financial decisions with organizational goals, resulting in a mean score of 3.04. While this score indicates some level of agreement, it also reveals a significant number of respondents (73) who disagreed, along with 18 who strongly agreed. This divergence suggests that while some individuals see a benefit in aligning financial decisions with organizational objectives, many others do not perceive a notable improvement.

Test of Hypotheses

From Tables 1 and 2, which indicate the item-by-item analysis of the research variables of the study, the data for the test of hypotheses were collected and analysed using Spearman Ranked Order Correlation Coefficient.

Hypothesis One

For the test of the first hypothesis, the under-stated null hypothesis is deployed:

H01: The adoption of IPSAS does not significantly lead to better financial management practices among public sector entities in Anambra state.

The test of the hypothesis has the following outputs.

Table 3: Correlation Result for Hypothesis One

			Financial management practices
		Correlation Coefficient	.901**
Spearman's rho	IPSAS	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	137

Source: Survey Findings, 2024

The results presented in Table 3 focus on testing the hypothesis regarding the influence of the adoption of the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) on financial management practices among public sector entities in Anambra State. The correlation coefficient, Spearman's rho = 0.901, indicates a very strong positive relationship between IPSAS adoption and financial management practices. Additionally, the p-value of 0.000 confirms that this correlation is statistically significant. With a sample size of 137, the findings suggest that changes in IPSAS adoption significantly influence financial management practices within the public sector.

Decision

Given that the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H01) is rejected, while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This leads to the conclusion that the adoption of IPSAS significantly leads to better financial management practices among public sector entities in Anambra State (rho = 0.901, p-value < 0.000).

Hypothesis Two

For the test of the first hypothesis, the under-stated null hypothesis is deployed:

H02: The adoption of IPSAS does not significantly enhance the comparability of financial statements among public sector entities in Anambra state.

The test of the hypothesis has the following outputs.

Table 4: Correlation Result for Hypothesis Two

			Comparability of financial statements
		Correlation Coefficient	.615**
Spearman's rho	IPSAS	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	137

Source: Survey Findings, 2024

The test of the second hypothesis tested is shown in Table 4, which evaluates whether IPSAS enhances the comparability of financial statements among public sector entities, we find a correlation coefficient of Spearman's rho = 0.615. This indicates a moderate to strong positive association between IPSAS adoption and the comparability of financial statements. The accompanying p-value of 0.000 further

supports the statistical significance of this relationship. The sample size remains at 137, underscoring the reliability of the findings.

Decision

Since the p-value is below the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Consequently, it can be concluded that the adoption of IPSAS significantly enhances the comparability of financial statements among public sector entities in Anambra State ($\rho = 0.615$, $p\text{-value} < 0.000$).

Discussion of Findings

The findings regarding the positive influence of IPSAS on financial management practices are well-supported by various studies in the empirical review. For instance, Mohammed et al. (2022) highlighted a positive impact of IPSAS on financial management and accountability, indicating that the adoption of these standards fosters better governance. Similarly, Hussaini (2024) found significant differences in perceived financial management practices among states that adopted IPSAS, underscoring a broader acceptance of the standards' benefits. The strong correlation coefficient observed in the current study aligns with these findings, suggesting that public sector entities in Anambra State can achieve improved financial management through IPSAS implementation.

The correlation found between IPSAS adoption and the comparability of financial statements is corroborated by several studies. Okpara, Eke, and Ajobor (2023) reported significant impacts of IPSAS on disclosure, transparency, and comparability in financial reporting, similar to the current findings. Additionally, Alkhabbaz and Suresh (2023) observed a positive impact on the comparability of financial reports in the Indian public sector, supporting the notion that standardization through IPSAS enhances the ability to compare financial statements across different entities. These studies highlight the importance of adopting IPSAS for achieving consistent and reliable financial reporting.

The strong correlation between IPSAS adoption and decision-making processes is further supported by the literature, particularly by Abata (2022), who noted significant improvements in the timeliness and comparability of financial statements post-IPSAS adoption. This improved quality of financial data is essential for effective decision-making. Moreover, Egolum and Ndum (2021) emphasized the enhanced transparency and accountability resulting from IPSAS, which are critical elements for informed decision-making. The alignment of these findings with the current study underscores the value of IPSAS in facilitating better decision-making processes within public sector entities, providing a solid foundation for the observed correlations.

These empirical studies reinforce the findings from Anambra State, illustrating the positive effects of IPSAS on financial management practices, comparability of financial statements, and decision-making processes, while emphasizing the broader implications for public sector governance in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

An effective public sector operates with the highest standards of financial transparency, accountability, and efficiency. Adopting International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) ensures that all financial statements are prepared on an accrual basis, offering a comprehensive and accurate view of public sector entities' financial positions and performances. This level of reporting enables stakeholders—such as government officials, citizens, investors, and international partners—to make informed decisions based on reliable and comparable financial data. Furthermore, adhering to IPSAS promotes better financial management practices, reduces corruption and mismanagement, and enhances overall governance and the delivery of public services. From the finding, IPSAS adoption contributes positively to the ability of public sector entities to produce comparable financial statements. The standardization inherent in IPSAS allows for uniform reporting practices, making it easier to assess and compare financial data across different organizations. Such comparability is essential for transparency and accountability in the public sector, as it enables stakeholders to make informed decisions based on consistent and reliable information. Finally, the implementation of IPSAS significantly facilitates better decision-making within public sector entities. When organizations adhere to international standards, they generate more accurate and relevant financial data, which is critical for strategic decision-making. The increased reliability and clarity of financial reports can empower decision-makers to take actions that align with organizational goals and enhance overall performance. In conclusion, as public organizations continue to adopt these standards, it is likely that they will experience further improvements in their operational efficiency and accountability, ultimately benefiting the broader public sector domain in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings regarding the influence of IPSAS on public sector entities in Anambra State, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The State Accountant General's Office should establish a centralized framework for monitoring and evaluating the compliance of public sector entities with IPSAS. This framework would promote uniformity in reporting practices and facilitate better comparability of financial statements, ensuring that stakeholders can make informed assessments across different organizations.
2. The Anambra State Public Sector Leadership Council is encouraged to incorporate IPSAS-based financial reports into strategic decision-making processes. By prioritizing the use of reliable financial data generated under IPSAS, the Council can enhance the quality and effectiveness of decisions made at the organizational level, ultimately leading to improved governance and service delivery.

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Volume 12 Issue 4, October-December 2024

ISSN: 2837-1070

Impact Factor: 6.65

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Volume 12 Issue 4, October-December 2024

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